

“Brute Willfulness”: History, Agency, and Human Sovereignty’s Wayward Animals

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Abstract:

This article situates itself in longstanding debates about forms and possibilities of animal agency under conditions of human control by mobilizing a concept that has received little theoretical attention from animal studies scholars. “Willfulness” – together with its close semantic cousins “obstinacy” and “self-will” – is defined by an insistence on autonomy (bodily, spatial, temporal) and self-direction in the face of heteronomous impositions. At its core, it can be understood as an embodied subject’s response to the experiential rift created between the capacity to perceive one’s environment and the freedom to engage with it in ways that align with one’s interests, needs, or desires. This article explores the utility of this concept for (historical) animal studies, specifically with respect to the relations between animal agency and the routines of human sovereignty at work in the exploitation of animal labor. To do this, I turn to German historian Alf Lüdtke’s (1943–2019) work on *Eigensinn*, a concept he employed to identify the spatial and temporal niches of “willful freedom” and forms of “willful corporeality” that factory workers in the decades around 1900 managed to carve out for themselves amid the disciplinary and regulatory mechanisms of the industrial labor regime. Lüdtke stressed that *Eigensinn* was not the “turning against” often equated with resistance but registered a leaving out of account, a turning *away* from sovereignty. Drawing on examples

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from my own historical research in the U.S. context, I underline the extent to which willfulness operated as an explanatory framework in recurring practical confrontations with unwanted animal behavior, indexing an implicit folk theory of animal mind in which working animals figured (for better or worse) as willing subjects with interests, desires, motivations, and tendencies of their own, and often exasperatingly at odds with a more or less clearly articulated cluster of human demands and expectations.

Keywords: agency, resistance, willfulness, obstinacy, *Eigensinn*, human-animal relations, animal history, U.S. history

We pay for their loyalty: they can be willful, hard to catch, dangerous to shoe, and buck on frosty mornings. In turn, they'll work themselves into a lather cutting cows, not for the praise they'll get but for the simple glory of outdodging a calf or catching up with an errant steer. The outlaws in a horse herd earn their ominous names – the red roan called Bonecrusher, the sorrel gelding referred to as Widowmaker. Others are talented but insist on having things their own way.²

Introduction

Near the end of his life, Nehemias Tjernagel, an Iowa farmer, musician, and avid traveler born in 1868, published a series of articles in the *Annals of Iowa* offering his reminiscences of a time of “winding prairie trails and cattle paths” before the arrival of increasing numbers of settlers on the western grasslands.³ Among other topics, Tjernagel’s narrative is interspersed with anecdotes of life and work with domesticated animals, who helped settlers overcome human bodily limitations and environmental challenges as they established themselves on the prairies. Rather than a human figure that stood “solitary and alone in the offing of the vast prairie-spaces,” western “pioneers” not only commonly appeared in the plural and relied on “concentric rings of support” – from the immediate family to loose settler neighborhoods to familial networks outside the region – they were also embedded in tightly knit webs of more-than-human interdependency.⁴ Vital to any success on western land, domesticated animals not only provided the living infrastructure that enabled settler mobility and expansion but assumed

² Gretel Ehrlich, *The Solace of Open Spaces* (Viking Penguin, 1985), 64.

³ Nehemias Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” *The Annals of Iowa* 31, no. 8 (1953): 600.

⁴ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 595; Elliott West, *The Way to the West: Essays on the Central Plains* (University of New Mexico Press, 1995), 96.

an important cultural role as living testimony to the capacity of transforming the natural world in a way befitting of self-identified “civilized” humanity. They embodied the interlacing of settler sovereignty – the claim to ultimate governing power over Indigenous lands and everything that happened on and with them – with the more longstanding structuring principle of *human* sovereignty, which legitimized the near-absolute authority over animals’ lives, bodies, and movements, including their exposure to or protection from violence and their very morphological, physiological, and behavioral characteristics.

Yet settlers like the Tjernagels also knew all too well that this mobilization of nonhuman capacities for their human projects came with an asterisk that marked the conditional, negotiated nature of animal participation. Unlike instrumental extensions or enhancements of human agency like axes or plows, their nonhuman co-laborers were living creatures with interests, desires, motivations, and tendencies of their own not usually in sync with human expectations. As Richard White reminds us, while it is true that settlers “would have neither survived nor conquered” without their animals, the latter “often proved fickle allies” who repeatedly “turn[ed] against their masters’ purposes,” a fact that led to a broad spectrum of consequences and “greatly complicated the history and the mental and physical landscape of the West.”⁵ If domesticated animals were tools of human power, they were so only in the limited sense of tools that repeatedly contested their toolhood – not necessarily through conscious revolt but simply by way of a sentient aliveness that had to be persuaded, compelled, or accommodated to ensure its alignment with human demands.

Emblematic of this inescapable friction, Tjernagel’s reminiscences of Iowa pioneer life are populated by a motley menagerie of “restless bulls,” “adventurous rams,” “missing horses,”

⁵ Richard White, “Animals and Enterprise,” in *The Oxford History of the American West*, ed. Clyde A. Milner et al. (Oxford University Press, 1994), 238.

and “foraging porkers.”⁶ Among other episodes, he recounts the story of a neighbor’s “awkward experience with his usually tractable ox-team” on a trip to Nevada, which Tjernagel considers a perfect example of the various episodes of “brute willfulness” that punctuated everyday life with domesticated animals.⁷ Having taken a keen interest in visiting a creek some distance from the road, any attempt at commanding the two oxen was “like addressing the Sphinx,” as “the stubborn pair pursued their course unimpressed, intent on the object of their desire.”⁸ The bovines had been given copious amounts of water only recently and – “according to precedent” – should have been “fully appeased” – but be it in human or animal affairs, “things are not always gauged by what has gone before.”⁹ Empathizing with his neighbor’s frustrations, Tjernagel explains that “[w]hat makes a man the more exasperated in any such futile effort to control the situation, is that he is so completely left out of account by the chief actors; all he can do is to nurse his own impotency, frantic gesticulations and emphatic language to the contrary.”¹⁰ Rather than defying human impositions in any direct sense, the bovine duo advanced to the position of “chief actors” simply by remaining “unimpressed,” by refusing any ground of interaction that might distract them from the “object of their desire.” Unmoved by human authority, these “willful bovines of long ago” might as well have been “the Sphinx” – not the creature of mythology with a penchant for murderous riddles but the thoroughly irresponsive monolith whose gaze remains obstinately fixed on some point on the eastern horizon.¹¹

⁶ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 605, 606, 607.

⁷ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 596, 595.

⁸ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 596.

⁹ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 596.

¹⁰ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 596.

¹¹ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 596.

By mobilizing the language of willfulness – understood here as a semantic field that also includes a cluster of closely related terms like “obstinacy” and “self-will” – Tjernagel drew on an established folk theoretical grammar that attributed interiority, intention, and moral character to animal actions while negotiating the limits of human sovereignty. Tjernagel’s observations provide a fitting entry point for this article, which situates itself in longstanding debates about forms and possibilities of animal agency under changing conditions of human control and exploitation, and the descriptive registers and analytical tools we use to make sense of them. The concept of “resistance” has loomed large in these debates, not only as an explicit focus of theoretical and political attention but also as an implicit framing device for thinking about animal agency more generally.¹² Resistance has proved a productive lens for thinking about animals’ abilities to “push back against the pressures and presumptions of the human-dominated world” and subvert human designs in various historical, environmental, and institutional contexts.¹³ The prominence of resistance is perhaps also an acknowledgment of the specifically “Anthropocenic” iterations of human sovereignty, which have multiplied and

¹² Bob Carter and Nickie Charles, “Animals, Agency and Resistance,” *Journal for the Theory of Social Behaviour* 43, no. 3 (2013): 322–40; Chris Wilbert, “Anti-This-Against-That: Resistances Along a Human-Nonhuman Axis,” in *Entanglements of Power: Geographies of Domination/Resistance*, ed. Joanne P. Sharp et al. (Routledge, 2000); Jason C. Hribal, *Fear of the Animal Planet: The Hidden History of Animal Resistance* (AK Press, 2010); Chris Pearson, “Beyond ‘Resistance’: Rethinking Nonhuman Agency for a ‘More-Than-Human’ World,” *European Review of History* 22, no. 5 (2015): 709–25; Sarat Colling, *Animal Resistance in the Global Capitalist Era* (Michigan State University Press, 2021); Violette Pouillard, “The Silence and the Fury: Addressing Animal Resistance and Agency through the History of Human-Animal Relationships,” in *Animals Matter: Resistance and Transformation in Animal Commodification*, ed. Julien Dugnoille (Brill, 2023).

¹³ Philip Howell, “Animals, Agency, and History,” in *The Routledge Companion to Animal-Human History*, ed. Hilda Kean and Philip Howell (Routledge, 2018), 204.

intensified relations of domination, as animal lifeworlds have become more severely circumscribed by human intervention and encroachment.

However, the concept has been questioned as to its capacity to conceptually accommodate a diversity of animal ways of “acting otherwise” without flattening the spectrum of possible motivations, purposes, and affordances that such behaviors might attest to. Some, like Chris Pearson, have criticized an anthropomorphic tendency to imagine animals “as plucky, courageous and cunning human-like resisters.”¹⁴ But instead of motivating an uncritical anthropomorphism, the concept might just as well work in the opposite direction. Perhaps in discovering all too many instances of animal resistance, we run the risk of introducing a new kind of “animal machine,” an impoverished animal subject whose behaviors are no longer determined by the rigid action patterns of instinct but by a similarly schematic logic of opposition that makes it increasingly difficult to think about animal agency in anything other than a purely reactive frame. If we grant that, even within anthropogenically circumscribed lifeworlds, animal agency is not simply overdetermined by human projects, then we need to resist the tendency to subsume all forms of animal behavior that fail to meet human expectations under the rubric of resistance.

This article argues that willfulness offers a useful heuristic lens to complicate and complement the analytical toolkit we draw on to make sense of the spectrum of ways in which animals inhabit, act in, and appropriate human-imposed orders, investing them with a sense of “ownness” by selectively adopting, bending, or reworking their routines and arrangements. Like resistance, willfulness speaks to agency within relations of domination in which a desire for behavioral autonomy tends to clash with a set of heteronomous impositions, often centered on the extraction of labor. And like resistance, it addresses the gap between how systems of

¹⁴ Pearson, “Beyond ‘Resistance,’” 720.

control are imagined or intended by humans and how they are actually lived and shaped by unwanted or unexpected forms of animal agency. Rather than re- or displacing resistance as a concept, willfulness thus identifies a broader range of behaviors under conditions of human control that underline animals' own subjective investments and worldmaking practices. If we understand as forms of *resistance* the ways in which animals turn *against* human impositions, willfulness foregrounds a self-assertive turning *toward* that is perhaps better understood as forms of *insistence* – behaviors through which animals carve out bodily, spatial, and temporal zones of autonomy within human-imposed orders by pursuing their own lines of action, preferences, and attachments alongside or in spite of human demands. I suggest that historians may approach willfulness from both an etic and an emic perspective – as an analytic heuristic for discussing forms of (historical) animal agency that exceed a strictly oppositional frame and as a historical category through which people in the past evaluated such behaviors – to draw out the co-constitutive dynamic between animal conduct and human meaning-making.

In what follows, I first discuss the historical life of willfulness as a behavioral category that marks the zone of friction between willing selves and their individual projects and a social order whose functioning was tied to a set of norms and hierarchies that set limits to legitimate forms of self-assertion. Focusing on nineteenth-century discourse, this historical perspective allows us to identify willfulness as a semantic field through which people organized and evaluated disruptive departures in the behavior of animals from the roles and tasks imposed upon them, whether as an explicit lexicon that mobilized a cluster of relevant signal terms or as an underlying grammar that registered animal subjectivity from within a particular normative frame to police or reaffirm the boundaries of acceptable conduct. I then offer some theoretical reflections on the concept and its analytical potential within broader debates on animal agency and resistance, drawing on German historian Alf Lüdtke's conceptual-historical work on *Eigensinn*. In a final section, I turn to my own research on human-animal relations in

the context of nineteenth-century U.S. westward expansion, focusing on overland travel as a site where willfulness took shape in the frictions between animal interests, human demands, and environmental contingencies.

The Problem of the Will

The English word “will” (derived from Old English *willan*) historically covers a wide semantic terrain reaching from desire, wish, and inclination to deliberate mental acts of intending or choosing to do something. Over time, its verbal form came to function as a basic future auxiliary, partially obscuring older associations with desire and choice while retaining its sense of directedness toward a future state or object. If “will” implied volition, the related “shall” implied obligation, and so the pair established a contrast between self-directed and externally shaped or prescribed futurity. The will’s “linguistic biography” has thus carved a “tumultuous path . . . of semantic and syntactic shifts,” yielding a rich yet ambiguous landscape of meanings and connotations “ranging from inner subjective life to external social dictates.”¹⁵ It is this enduring tension between subjective projects of self-realization and the heteronomous play of forces seeking to contain or appropriate them that willfulness brings into focus. However, unlike its generally positive present-day connotations with forms of creative self-assertion or principled refusal in the face of unjust authority, in its historical usage willfulness predominantly identified displays of disobedience or nonconformance on the part of social “inferiors” or “dependents” that illegitimately undermined social norms and hierarchies.

¹⁵ Keith M. Murphy and C. Jason Throop, “Willing Contours: Locating Volition in Anthropological Theory,” in *Toward an Anthropology of the Will*, ed. Keith M. Murphy and C. Jason Throop (Stanford University Press, 2010), 6, 7. Also see Sara Ahmed, *Willful Subjects* (Duke University Press, 2014), 31–32.

The will – “one of philosophy’s most promiscuous terms” – lost much of its conceptual standing and became increasingly sidelined in the philosophical mainstream of the last century, but it was a topic of significant philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical concern throughout most of the nineteenth century.¹⁶ As it was understood by contemporaries, “the will was, at one and the same time, something given, in an inherited constitution, something shaped by experience, something modified by the very habits that it itself gave rise to, and something that was subject to action upon, by self or by others.”¹⁷ For those working in the field of “mental philosophy” – a major precursor to philosophy of mind – understanding the will and its role in shaping human conduct was key to the development of “a science of human action” that could be distinguished both from “the actions of physical forces, such as waterpower, steam-power, or electricity” and from the domain of “animal impulse, such as the craving of hunger, fear of danger, or rage against an adversary.”¹⁸ Debates about the will and its manifestations commonly presumed an integral connection between *willing* and *moving* selves, tying articulations of volitional agency to the capacity for self-movement in a way that blurred any strict separation between mental and physical domains. New York physician David Meredith Reese argued that, together with “sensibility,” the “voluntary power” that enabled self-movement, and to whose existence outwardly observable actions provided testimony, was one

¹⁶ Ahmed, *Willful Subjects*, 5. Gilbert Ryle rejected the concept, especially in the sense of a “Faculty, immaterial Organ, or Ministry,” arguing that it had “no utility.” Gilbert Ryle, *The Concept of Mind* (Hutchinson, 1949), 63, 62. One prominent counterexample is Hannah Arendt’s *The Life of the Mind* (1977–1978), which devotes one of its two volumes to the topic. For a discussion, see Suzanne Jacobitti, “Hannah Arendt and the Will,” *Political Theory* 16, no. 1 (1988): 53–76.

¹⁷ Nikolas Rose, “Governing the Will in a Neurochemical Age,” in *On Willing Selves: Neoliberal Politics Vis-à-Vis the Neuroscientific Challenge*, ed. Sabine Maasen and Barbara Sutter (Palgrave Macmillan, 2007), 82.

¹⁸ Henry Calderwood, “The Problem Concerning the Human Will, as Related to Scientific and Philosophic Theories,” *The Princeton Review* 54 (September 1878): 332.

of the “two chief characteristics of animals.”¹⁹ Generating the mental force that drove and explained action, the will took on a quasi-physiological existence, becoming legible in the movements it produced.²⁰ According to Thomas C. Upham, professor of mental and moral philosophy at Bowdoin College, regardless of the variance of opinion on the issue there was still a “general agreement . . . that the mind, both in its internal constitution and in its adaptation to outward objects, is evidently framed for movement,” and that in explaining how “the various parts of man’s nature conspire to action,” one had to look to the will as its “ultimate seat and source.”²¹ The will was thus understood as first cause, prompting a sequence of willed events that reverberated across physiological, political, and moral registers. It was the “controlling and executive power of the mind,” and its most important product was “*outward* action.”²² Jonathan Baldwin Turner, a former professor at Illinois College and the first president of the Illinois State Natural History Society, explained that the archer who “wills to pull his bow-string” activated “a series of forces, animal and natural,” that led from the mysterious voluntary power hidden within the reaches of the mind to the perceptible actions it produced, “determining life and death, or, it may be, the fate of armies and empires. But, as in all other possible cases, here is only, first, a self-moving power of some voluntary being.”²³

¹⁹ David Meredith Reese, *Elements of Zoology; or, Natural History of Animals* (Barnes, 1849), 11, emphases removed.

²⁰ Roger Smith, “The Physiology of the Will: Mind, Body, and Psychology in the Periodical Literature, 1855–1875,” in *Science Serialized: Representation of the Sciences in Nineteenth-Century Periodicals*, ed. Geoffrey Cantor and Sally Shuttleworth (MIT Press, 2004).

²¹ Thomas C. Upham, *A Philosophical and Practical Treatise on the Will* (William Hyde, 1834), 38.

²² Upham, *Treatise on the Will*, 39, original emphasis.

²³ Jonathan Baldwin Turner, “Power, Force and Matter: Their Diversity, Unity, Simplicity and Harmony, the Basis of All Science and All Knowledge,” in *Transactions of the Illinois Natural History Society* (1861), 1:25, emphases removed.

The “executive” powers of the will could become a problem when the latter was either deficiently or excessively developed.²⁴ The internationally debated case of the German youth Kaspar Hauser exemplified the former phenomenon – an “extreme extinction” of the will, where everything appeared to be “wrapped up in slumber and inactivity” to such an extent that the “slightest impulse from the minds of others was followed by the consentaneous and unresisting movement of his own,” much like “the flexible reed of the desert, which, without knowing the power that presses it, is shaken and bent by every changing breeze.”²⁵ In such cases, volitional agency threatened to become indistinguishable from the mechanistic causalities of the very natural forces that mental philosophers sought to distinguish it from. An *overdevelopment* of the will, in contrast, produced forms of behavior that contemporaries referred to as “willful,” a designation that identified the will, and the willing self, as a *problem* – specifically, as a problem for the exercise of authority, and thus as a privileged site of intervention.²⁶ Closest in meaning to willfulness were the terms “self-will” and “obstinacy” – a “fixedness in” or “unreasonable adherence to an opinion, purpose or system . . . that will not yield to persuasion, arguments or other means” and could not “be shaken at all, or not without great difficulty.”²⁷ For some, such *idées fixes* were also associated with a “perverse” disposition

²⁴ See G. E. Berrios and M. Gili, “Will and Its Disorders: A Conceptual History,” *History of Psychiatry* 6, no. 21 (1995); Roger Smith, “Mental Disorder, Criminal Responsibility and the Social History of Theories of Volition,” *Psychological Medicine* 9, no. 1 (1979): 13–19; Mariana Valverde, *Diseases of the Will: Alcohol and the Dilemmas of Freedom* (Cambridge University Press, 1998).

²⁵ Upham, *Treatise on the Will*, 37, 38.

²⁶ Leslie Irvine, *If You Tame Me: Understanding Our Connection with Animals* (Temple University Press, 2004), 128; Ahmed, *Willful Subjects*, 3.

²⁷ Webster, *American Dictionary*, under “willfulness,” “self-will,” “obstinacy.” Some argued that obstinacy resulted not from an overly developed but from a *weakness* of will. See Theodate L. Smith, “Obstinacy and

to “cross or vex,” one that was “uncomplying, unaccommodating or acting in opposition to what is proper or what is desired by others.”²⁸ It was this kind of insistent self-assertion that G. W. F. Hegel diagnosed as a false form of freedom that remained unable to emancipate itself from what it opposed. For Hegel, the freedom of “having a ‘mind of one’s own’” was a kind of freedom “still enmeshed in servitude.”²⁹

Wherever it sprang from, willfulness disrupted social hierarchies on the level of lived praxis, making it a prominent target for corrective or disciplinary pedagogical interventions. In children, it had to be eradicated systematically and resolutely *before* it became unmanageable – through gentle instruction and persuasion, if possible, through calculated physical correction, if necessary. James Mott, husband of abolitionist and women’s rights activist Lucretia Mott, advised that “[t]he first inclination a child discovers, is the gratification of will. The first business therefore of education is its subjection.”³⁰ Failing this, “a child’s will becomes incorrigible; and then severity is resorted to in order to bring [it] into subjection,” which came with significant risk in its own right, because when willfulness was “made sullenly to submit to superior strength forcibly exerted,” it was likely to remain “unsubdued,” leading to a “much to be dreaded spirit of revenge.”³¹ Henry Immanuel Smith’s *Education* warned that willful behavior, “a striving for independence of control, without reference to any particular purpose,”

Obedience: A Study in the Psychology and Pedagogy of the Will,” *The Pedagogical Seminary* 12, no. 1 (1905): 43–44.

²⁸ Webster, *American Dictionary*, under “perverseness.”

²⁹ Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, *Phenomenology of Spirit*, trans. A. V. Miller (Oxford University Press, 1977), 119.

³⁰ James Mott, *Observations on the Education of Children, and Hints to Young People on the Duties of Civil Life* (Printed by Samuel Wood and Sons, 1816), 2.

³¹ Mott, *Observations*, 3, 4.

was among “the first definite forms in which degeneracy is manifested in children.”³² If the child in question had a “contemplative temperament,” this “degeneracy” took the form of “pure obstinacy, as a feeling which submits with repugnance to foreign control,” while more active children – especially boys, in Smith’s gendered framing – exhibited self-will: “they seek to rule, and refuse to be guided by others.”³³ What united these perspectives was the conviction that willfulness, if left unchecked, was likely to solidify into its own kind of counter-sovereignty: a problematic doubling of the power otherwise monopolized by parents, educators, clergy, and other authority figures.

It was an implicit prerequisite that willfulness was only to be understood (and condemned) as such when the authority it undermined was an expression of a legitimate social order to whose functioning it contributed. This prerequisite allowed *American Slavery as It Is* (1839), an anonymously published collection of eyewitness accounts compiled by Theodore D. Weld and the sisters Angelina and Sarah Grimké, to flip the evaluative script of willfulness for abolitionist purposes. In the case of slavery, it was the social order itself that was illegitimate – a tyrannical subjugation of fellow human beings – and in the absence of open rebellion, willfulness was its logical product. Besides defending the abolitionist claim that enslavers treated their human chattel not merely *like* but *worse than* animals with an array of examples and testimony, *American Slavery* attempted an explanation of the violence it sought to highlight, which appeared gratuitous even by the institution’s own oppressive standards. It was precisely because enslaved people shared all of the attributes of human nature – and were intuitively understood to do so even (or especially) by the most vicious of enslavers – that disobedience on their part repeatedly “provoked” outbursts of wrath. Willfulness implied the workings of a (human) intelligence in its source. Yet enslaved people were human *property*,

³² Henry Immanuel Smith, *Education* (Harper and Brothers, 1842), 302, also see 305–9.

³³ Smith, *Education*, 302.

and “*property* having a *will* . . . in opposition to the will of its owner” was “a stimulant of terrible power to the most relentless human passions.”³⁴

If horses and dogs were intelligent beings, and still held as property, their opposition to the wishes of their owner would exasperate them immeasurably more than it would be possible for them to do with the minds of brutes. None but little children and idiots get angry at sticks and stones that lie in their way or hurt them; but put into sticks and stones intelligence, and will, and power of feeling and motion, while they remain as now, articles of property, and what a towering rage would men be in, if bushes whipped them in the face when they walked among them, or stones rolled over their toes when they climbed hills!³⁵

Not merely presupposing a clear distinction between the human mind and the “minds of brutes,” the text seamlessly moves from the latter to the inorganic sphere of “sticks and stones,” relegating animal minds to a zone of ambiguity between the intelligence discernible in human forms of behavior and the seeming absurdity of intelligent, willing, and feeling stones.

The authors of *American Slavery* were not alone in linking the operations of the will to an account of human exceptionality. And yet, the widespread use of the language of willfulness in relation to animal behavior speaks to a more inclusive idea of volition as a principle that refused containment within the ontological boundaries of the human, testifying to a widespread folk psychological acknowledgment of animal subjectivity that interpreted the actions of animals – and their withholding of such actions – as the unmistakable product of (un)willing nonhuman selves. According to Webster’s *American Dictionary*, a “willful man” was someone

³⁴ Theodore D. Weld et al., *American Slavery as It Is: Testimony of a Thousand Witnesses* (American Anti-Slavery Society, 1839), 111.

³⁵ Weld et al., *American Slavery*, 111, original emphases.

who was “[g]overned by the will without yielding to reason,” a person in whom the close integration of the will and the intellect that characterized “normal” adults had been replaced by a dictatorship of the former; a “willful horse,” on the other hand, was “refractory” because the horse’s will stymied the actualization of *human* will through, with, or on the animal body.³⁶ If unsentimental observers conceded that domesticated animals should be regarded as “captives of our will” rather than “loyal subjects in the bonds of love,” willfulness called into question even this somewhat unflattering assessment.³⁷

The common injunction to systematically subdue willfulness as early as possible rested on a developmental logic that bridged human and animal worlds. Among the reasons listed by agricultural writers for a resolute early education of animals, one was that in young animals willfulness could not yet be fully articulated through superior physical force. The animal will had to be mastered – and that mastery naturalized – *before* it could know its own strength, and for this it was crucial to accustom animals to being handled by humans when they were still “too young to resist.”³⁸ The earlier one began training one’s animals “for the purposes to which we design to appropriate them, the more *willingly* and *naturally* they will fulfil those purposes,” inculcating in the animal “in the morning of its existence, ere yet its strength leads to obstinacy, that man is its superior, and that its movements must be directed by his will.”³⁹ This principle also informed the widely discussed training system developed by influential Ohio “horse whisperer” John Solomon Rarey. As one of his students revealed, the secret to success in Rarey’s system of “nonviolent” education lay in the fact that a colt “has originally no

³⁶ Webster, *American Dictionary*, under “willful”, emphases removed.

³⁷ Charles W. Webber, *The Hunter-Naturalist: Romance of Sporting; or, Wild Scenes and Wild Hunters* (J. W. Bradley, 1851), 37.

³⁸ A. Churchill, “Management of Stock,” *Prairie Farmer* 3, no. 3 (1843): 50.

³⁹ W. Bacon, “Training Domestic Animals,” *The Cultivator* 4, no. 4 (1847): 122, original emphases.

conception of his own strength or powers,” and to instill obedience it was advisable to keep the animal “in ignorance,” preventing him from learning “by trial that he could oppose your will.”⁴⁰

Advice books on the training of domesticated or captive animals proposed a range of corrective and disciplinary techniques directly aimed at eliminating willfulness. *Haney's Art of Training Animals* (1869), a popular and frequently advertised illustrated guide, included recommendations on the training of both common and “exotic” creatures (like monkeys and elephants). Whatever animal one was dealing with, “constant repetition” was of the utmost importance, and when given proper instruction animals would “in almost all cases comply with your wishes promptly and cheerfully,” which generally made punishment not only unnecessary but counterproductive, “unless the animal is willful, which is rare.”⁴¹ In the instance of horses who kept trying to run away or simply moved when they weren't supposed to, advice books recommended eradicating willfulness through a simple means of bodily manipulation: putting on a foot strap and lifting up the foot every time the animal attempted to run. “Should your horse be of the extremely willful character, he may run on three legs,” but the addition of a second strap on the opposite foot “will destroy his confidence in short order.”⁴² Yet as already emphasized by Mott, such “powerful means” of impressing “your subject with a sense of mastery” and “his inability to resist the will of man” were to be applied with circumspection, given that, in animals no less than in children, “[t]yranny and abuse inspires rebellion and

⁴⁰ “How Mr. Rarey Tames Horses,” *Harper's Weekly* 2, no. 84 (1858): 509, 510.

⁴¹ *Haney's Art of Training Animals: A Practical Guide for Amateur or Professional Trainers* (Jesse Haney, 1869), 15.

⁴² Dennis Magner and A. H. Rockwell, *A New System of Training Horses, by Which the Wildest Colts and Most Vicious Horses Can Be Thoroughly and Safely Subdued on a Practical and Improved Basis of Control* (Pierce and Budlong, 1863), 38.

Fig. 1: Teaching a horse to stop on command. *Haney's Art of Training Animals: A Practical Guide for Amateur or Professional Trainers* (New York: Jesse Haney, 1869), 24.

vengeance in the minds of the oppressed.”⁴³ According to a 1905 study by Clark University psychologist Theodate Smith based on 1418 reported cases of (mostly) children and 237 cases of animals, those tasked with governing human or animal dependents could learn to look for certain “bodily reactions” that functioned as “an index of approaching obstinacy,” allowing responsible parties to take action before the phenomenon fully manifested itself.⁴⁴

Willfulness, Agency, and *Eigensinn*

A matter of concern for overlapping projects of human pedagogy and animal management, willfulness marks volition as a site of regulation and intervention. It names troubling articulations of agency that destabilize hierarchized norms and routines of interaction and the behavioral circumscriptions designed to secure them. The seeming pervasiveness of such

⁴³ Magner and Rockwell, *A New System of Training Horses*, 38, 39.

⁴⁴ Smith, “Obstinacy and Obedience,” 27, 28.

disruptions and the resulting need for elaborate systems of control suggests an irreducible and insistent vitality of living beings willing to tolerate no more than a limited degree of heteronomous imposition. Animal willfulness manifests itself in the difficulty of transmuting human will into corresponding animal behavior and thus captures reclamations of autonomy under conditions generally designed to ensure the human capacity to “carry out will without (as well as despite) resistance.”⁴⁵ Impinged upon by the demands of human sovereignty, animal willfulness embodies a certain kind of power: “the power not to be compelled by an external force.”⁴⁶ It involves polymorphous assertions of autonomy on the level of embodied praxis – movements, in a figurative yet often also quite literal sense, that are best understood as movements away from, around, in excess, or short of rather than movements *against* human directives.

The tension between autonomy and heteronomy has also animated discussions around the meanings of “wildness,” a concept that not only evokes similar concerns for self-directed being and the limits (and ethics) of control but also shares deep etymological roots with “self-will.” This shared etymology is mobilized in an entry in Henry David Thoreau’s journal, whose project of reversing the predominantly negative valence of wildness among his contemporaries seemingly did not extend to the perception of willfulness. Remarking upon those “unsympathizing” people for whom the “virtue” of animals corresponded with their “tamableness,” Thoreau insisted that the hawk who would “not be poultry of yours, lays no eggs for you, [and] forever hides its nest” was certainly “*willed* or *wild*” but “not willful in its wildness.”⁴⁷ More recent commentators have tended to reclaim both wildness and willfulness

⁴⁵ Ahmed, *Willful Subjects*, 54.

⁴⁶ Ahmed, *Willful Subjects*, 186.

⁴⁷ Henry David Thoreau, *Winter: From the Journal of Henry David Thoreau*, ed. H. G. O. Blake (Houghton Mifflin, 1887), 399, original emphases.

in more affirmative registers, drawing on the semantic proximity of the two to articulate forms of nonhuman autonomy emancipated from human projects. George Monbiot has proposed “self-willed land” as an alternative to the historically fraught term “wilderness” in reference to environments “governed not by human management but by their own processes.”⁴⁸ Gavin van Horn, explaining that “*wild* indicates autonomy and agency, a will to be, a unique expression of life,” critiques the prevalent “set of assumptions about the autonomous *self*” that often informs ideas about wildness, which, he argues, “reflect a truncated view of what constitutes *self-will*.”⁴⁹ Van Horn instead emphasizes the relational nature of wildness as a phenomenon situated within distributed ecological processes, although his choice of example – that the wildness of an individual oak tree is “actualized through the wild processes of a community”⁵⁰ – leaves open the question whether wildness understood in terms of self-will requires at least *some* kind of willing self. Finally, Clare Palmer homes in on the relationship between animal individuals and human systems of control by proposing the term “self-willed wildness” for contexts where animals are “free from human or ‘civilizational’ constraints in expressing or fulfilling essential capacities, behaviors (often species-specific ones) and, in species where this applies, purposes and desires.”⁵¹

Monbiot’s and Palmer’s accounts in particular seem to predicate their ideas of wild “freedom” upon an escape from heteronomy. In my view, however, willfulness is better

⁴⁸ George Monbiot, *Feral: Rewilding the Land, the Sea, and Human Life* (The University of Chicago Press, 2014), 10.

⁴⁹ Gavin Van Horn, “Introduction: Into the Wildness,” in *Wildness: Relations of People and Place*, ed. Gavin Van Horn and John Hausdoerffer (University of Chicago Press, 2017), 2, 3, original emphases.

⁵⁰ Van Horn, “Into the Wildness,” 3.

⁵¹ Clare Palmer, “Climate Change, Ethics, and the Wildness of Wild Animals,” in *Animal Ethics in the Age of Humans: Blurring Boundaries in Human-Animal Relationships*, ed. Bernice Bovenkerk and Jozef Keulartz (Springer, 2016), 137, 140, emphases removed.

positioned to productively *complicate* such perspectives and holds its greatest analytical value when it is employed to make sense not of freedom from but freedom *in* constraint; to identify spaces and situations where/when animals are (en)able(d) to do their “own thing” *within* rather than without systems of human control and exploitation. From this perspective, willfulness, understood not as an individual characteristic or property but as an emergent relational phenomenon, occurs in the frictional zones where/when sovereignty fails to secure submission and where/when structurally subordinated actors reconfigure the conditions that constrain them – in misalignments between command and response, in slippages between prescribed function and enacted behavior, in situations in which demands are at best partially met, tasks are appropriated for other ends, or behaviors undermine assigned roles. The enabling conditions of willfulness are thus tied to specific affordance landscapes characterized by spatial and temporal suspensions of sovereignty under conditions in which the exercise of the latter depends on the appropriation, rather than subjugation, of subordinate forms of agency.

A breadth of perspectives exists on the nature(s), forms, and scales of agency across various human and nonhuman and even living and nonliving domains, and animal agency debates have not happened in isolation from these broader considerations. While a discussion of these issues is beyond the scope of this article, my own interest in animal agency is tied to an understanding of animals as perspectival and experiential loci enmeshed in worlds of meaning and action that matter to them and which they actively co-construct in varying forms and degrees. Helen Steward links animal agency to a “subjective perspective of some kind” that enables animals to perceive and purposefully move through “a world of spatially and temporally ordered objects and events.”⁵² Their agential subjectivity turns animals into what Steward calls “settler[s] of matters,” connecting the capacity for self-movement (motility) to a

⁵² Helen Steward, *A Metaphysics for Freedom* (Oxford University Press, 2012), 72.

degree of underdetermination in that “the actions by means of which those movements are effected cannot be regarded merely as the inevitable consequences of what has gone before” but represent “newly initiated injections into the course of history” by an agent who “*responds* to incoming information and to the motivational effects of desire.”⁵³

The relationship between animal agency and human sovereignty has been historically and socially variable because different animals at different times in different places have confronted different iterations of this principle.⁵⁴ Generally speaking, however, insofar as animal agency has borne upon human projects, human sovereignty has demanded its confinement within often narrow margins of acceptability. It is specifically in the human exploitation of animal labor, however, that animal agency has been both indispensable and a constant source of friction. Animal labor is a phenomenon that encompasses a terrain of significant social and historical difference, sometimes truncated by an overemphasis on modern capitalist relations.⁵⁵ Because animal labor presupposes a degree of responsiveness and often relies on the mobilization of animal capacities, many labor arrangements have been structured in ways that tend to create opportunities for animals to act against, across, or simply outside of

⁵³ Steward, *Metaphysics for Freedom*, 78, original emphasis.

⁵⁴ On the modern capitalist context of human sovereignty, see Dinesh Wadiwel, *The War Against Animals* (Brill, 2015); Dinesh Wadiwel, *Animals and Capital* (Edinburgh University Press, 2023).

⁵⁵ On animal labor, see Jocelyne Porcher and Tiphaine Schmitt, “Dairy Cows: Workers in the Shadows?,” *Society & Animals* 20, no. 1 (2012): 39–60; Jocelyne Porcher and Jean Estebanez, “Animal Labor: At the Forefront of Innovative Research,” in *Animal Labor: A New Perspective on Human-Animal Relations*, ed. Jocelyne Porcher and Jean Estebanez (transcript, 2019); Jason Hribal, “Animals Are Part of the Working Class Reviewed,” *Borderlands* 11, no. 2 (2012); Maan Barua, “Animal Work: Metabolic, Ecological, Affective,” *Cultural Anthropology*, July 26, 2018, <https://www.culanth.org/fieldsights/animal-work-metabolic-ecological-affective>; Nicolas Delon, “The Meaning of Animal Labour,” in *Animal Labour: A New Frontier of Interspecies Justice?*, ed. Charlotte Blattner et al. (Oxford University Press, 2020).

human intentions. It is thus no surprise that historians have often been drawn to animal labor as an archive of the hidden – and not-so-hidden – transcripts of animal resistance, illuminating the myriad ways in which animals, in Susan Nance’s apt phrasing, have been “rejecting the conditions of their experience.”⁵⁶

The tendency to think about the agency of *domesticated* animals in particular in terms of resistance, and the implicit assumption that resistance is its primary – if not in fact its only “true” – manifestation, in part flows from the observation that domesticates are the most visible and consequential case of animals acting within or vis-à-vis human social structures and institutions. Domestication is now often understood in terms of a *longue durée* of co-evolutionary formations of interspecies life rather than simply something that humans have done to animals, a perspective that calls into question the extent to which this phenomenon can be understood as unambiguous testimony to human biospheric dominance. Yet it remains the case that especially in modern regimes of industrialized animal use, many domesticated environments have been refashioned into little more than apparatuses of capture and exploitation, creating animal lifeworlds that have become saturated by human economic interests. In this light, we need to be careful about how we accentuate animal agency and interspecies collaboration within relations of domination, lest we overcorrect at the expense of recognizing both the structural and everyday forms of violence and coercion – today often “materially and epistemically cloaked”⁵⁷ – that organize these relations.

⁵⁶ Susan Nance, *Entertaining Elephants: Animal Agency and the Business of the American Circus* (The Johns Hopkins University Press, 2013), 10. On the concept of “hidden transcripts,” see James C. Scott, *Domination and the Arts of Resistance: Hidden Transcripts* (Yale University Press, 1990).

⁵⁷ Wadiwel, *Animals and Capital*, 128.

Fig. 2: Animal agency in systems of human control. Leftward vectors represent variegated forms of insistence that do not primarily aim at opposition. Rightward vectors represent forms of resistance that contest heteronomous impositions in different degrees of intensity and visibility.

The efficacy of anthropogenic systems in regulating, directing, and curtailing animal behavior so as to best exploit animal labor has shaped what is intelligible *as* animal agency, which is why, as Vinciane Despret has pointed out, the agentiality of animal work tends to become visible almost exclusively in the moment of its disruption: when animals are able to frustrate or confound human horizons of expectation and “place limits on what can happen,

explicitly disobey, pretend not to understand, hide themselves, cheat.”⁵⁸ This emphasis is neither surprising nor peculiar to human–animal affairs, reflecting a broader tendency of historical and social inquiry to privilege moments of rupture, dysfunction, and failure – an orientation mirrored (and reinforced) by the archival and documentary biases historians regularly encounter in their work. Taken together, these epistemic habits may help explain our tendency to oscillate between what Andria Pooley-Ebert has referred to as the “defiance-dominance trap” in thinking about animal agency.⁵⁹ If the “dominance” side of this interpretive coin tends to foreclose serious consideration of animal agency, the “defiance” side struggles to make space for articulations of the latter that are not reducible to reactive disruptions or rejections of human sovereignty.

Thinking with willfulness might help us loosen this interpretive bind. It remains close to, and may even veer into, the semantic terrain of resistance, but it does so with an emphasis on animals’ pursuits of their own (micro)projects, and their insistence on doing so even under anthropogenic conditions of dependency and constraint. It may thus help us identify pockets or zones of relative autonomy within meshworks of dense heteronomous circumscriptions in the form of self-assertive reclamations of time, space, and/or mobility. I want to suggest that we can find one potent source of inspiration for such a framing of willfulness in German labor historian Alf Lüdtke’s (1943–2019) theoretico-historical work on *Eigensinn* (or *Eigen-Sinn*, in

⁵⁸ Vinciane Despret, “From Secret Agents to Interagency,” *History and Theory* 52, no. 4 (2013): 42. Also see Porcher and Schmitt, “Dairy Cows.”

⁵⁹ Andria Pooley-Ebert, “Species Agency: A Comparative Study of Horse-Human Relationships in Chicago and Rural Illinois,” in *The Historical Animal*, ed. Susan Nance (Syracuse University Press, 2015), 150.

his original spelling).⁶⁰ The meaning of *Eigensinn* is not easily captured by any single English-language equivalent. Its most direct translation is “one’s own sense,” but a useful entry in the glossary of the English translation of Lüdtké’s edited volume on *The History of Everyday Life* gives us a better understanding of its conceptual reach. Here, *Eigensinn* is said to denote

willfulness, spontaneous self-will, a kind of self-affirmation, . . . demarcating a space of one’s own In standard parlance, the word has pejorative overtones, referring to “obstreperous, obstinate” behavior, usually of children. The “discompounding” of writing it as *Eigen-Sinn* stresses its root signification of “one’s own sense, own meaning.”

It is semantically linked to *aneignen* (appropriate, reappropriate, reclaim).⁶¹

Lüdtké originally developed this concept to describe behaviors in the everyday life of late-nineteenth to mid-twentieth-century industrial workers that did not fit a simple dyadic model of “compliant” versus “resistant” forms of agency. Instead, Lüdtké argued that the behaviors he was interested in saw workers repeatedly create timespaces of “willful freedom” (*eigensinnige Freiheit*) for themselves, allowing them to establish “distance from sovereign impositions” (*herrschaftliche Zumutungen*).⁶²

For Lüdtké, *Eigensinn* was not a synonym for resistance, even if the boundaries between the two often “remained unclear and fluid” in historical practice.⁶³ Willful behaviors could be *in situ* and *ad hoc* occurrences that took place in “isolated moments,” but they often

⁶⁰ I thank Olaf Stieglitz for bringing this concept to my attention. Central to Lüdtké’s engagement with *Eigensinn* is his German-language study *Eigen-Sinn: Fabrikalltag, Arbeitererfahrungen und Politik vom Kaiserreich bis in den Faschismus* (1993; Westfälisches Dampfboot, 2015).

⁶¹ Alf Lüdtké, ed., *The History of Everyday Life: Reconstructing Historical Experiences and Ways of Life*, trans. William Templer (Princeton University Press, 1995), 313–14.

⁶² Lüdtké, *Eigen-Sinn*, 17. This and subsequent quotes are my own translation.

⁶³ Lüdtké, *Eigen-Sinn*, 130; also see 347–349.

consolidated into more elaborate patterns of conduct that repeatedly carved out a path between “open opposition” and “silent complaisance” in the face of “excessive manipulations and constraints.”⁶⁴ To some extent, Lüdtke’s conceptualization of *Eigensinn* thus resonates with what the late James C. Scott called “Brechtian forms of class struggle,” which relied on “the ordinary weapons of relatively powerless groups,” including such infra- or micropolitical practices as foot-dragging, dissimulation, and feigned ignorance.⁶⁵ Yet *Eigensinn* could also manifest as “horseplay” – that is, in the variety of practical jokes among workers themselves, “forms of expression [that] were not intended as resistance to impositions ‘from above’” but rather “occupied ‘space’ and ‘time’ for themselves.”⁶⁶

Lüdtke associated *Eigensinn* with “movements of evasion,” a phrase that can be understood broadly and figuratively as a refusal to subordinate one’s self to impositions originating from a power structure or center of authority but which also comprised a literal and embodied dimension of “willful corporeality” (*eigensinnige Körperlichkeit*).⁶⁷ This distinctly corporeal character of *Eigensinn* is already underlined by the fact that, at its most basic, the term *Eigensinn* signifies one’s “ownership of the five senses and therewith the power to

⁶⁴ Alf Lüdtke, “What Happened to the ‘Fiery Red Glow’? Workers’ Experiences and German Fascism,” in *The History of Everyday Life: Reconstructing Historical Experiences and Ways of Life*, ed. Alf Lüdtke, trans. William Templer (Princeton University Press, 1995), 227.

⁶⁵ James C. Scott, *Weapons of the Weak: Everyday Forms of Peasant Resistance* (Yale University Press, 1985), 29.

⁶⁶ Lüdtke, “What Happened to the ‘Fiery Red Glow,’” 227. In the preface to the 2015 edition of *Eigen-Sinn*, Lüdtke distinguished the term from “stubbornness” and “obstinacy.” For Lüdtke, these terms “tend more toward refusal, if not outright resistance,” instead of signifying the “‘ownness’ or ‘properness’ of the particular meaning, behavior, or endeavor in question,” pointing us to “the diverse practices of appropriation, of making the specific situation one’s own.” Lüdtke, *Eigen-Sinn*, 12–13.

⁶⁷ Lüdtke, “What Happened to the ‘Fiery Red Glow,’” 226; Lüdtke, *Eigen-Sinn*, 345.

perceive everything that occurs in one's environment" (*Sinn* signifying not only "meaning" but also the sensory apparatus itself).⁶⁸ The forms of behavior we might call willful or *eigensinnig* thus emerge from what Alexander Kluge and Oskar Negt's equal parts intriguing and confounding magnum opus *History and Obstinacy* – first published in German as *Geschichte und Eigensinn* (1981) – captures with the term "expropriation": the expropriation of basic capacities for embodied engagement, and the creation of an experiential rift between the ability to perceive one's environment and the freedom to engage with it in a way that corresponds with one's interests, needs, or desires.⁶⁹ As their translator Richard Langston puts it, *Eigensinn* "makes a claim to primitive property, one's right to one or more particularities that suddenly balk at any and all forms of exchange."⁷⁰

Discussing the reception of Lüdtkke's concept and its application to contexts other than German shop floors, Thomas Lindenberger notes that integral to *Eigensinn* is a certain provisionality and a "discreet undermining of a priori definitions and terms," making it "the opposite of a universal key, and hardly a patent recipe for 'solving' the riddles that remain after analyzing attitudes and behaviors."⁷¹ But, he insists, while the concept may require careful modification to make it responsive to different historical contexts and actors, it remains "fundamentally applicable to every object of investigation that includes a social component."⁷² Nothing in Lindenberger's text suggests that this claim is intended to encompass anything other

⁶⁸ Alexander Kluge and Oskar Negt, *History and Obstinacy*, ed. Devin Fore, trans. Richard Langston et al. (Zone Books, 2014), 292.

⁶⁹ *Eigensinn* is "the protest against expropriation reduced to a single point, the result of the expropriation of one's own senses that interface with the external world." Kluge and Negt, *History and Obstinacy*, 292.

⁷⁰ Richard Langston, *Dark Matter: A Guide to Alexander Kluge and Oskar Negt* (Verso, 2020), 276.

⁷¹ Thomas Lindenberger, "Eigen-Sinn, Domination and No Resistance," trans. David Burnett, *Docupedia-Zeitgeschichte*, August 3, 2015, https://docupedia.de/zg/Lindenberger_eigensinn_v1_en_2015.

⁷² Lindenberger, "Eigen-Sinn, Domination and No Resistance."

than human subjects and relations, but I want to make the case that key elements of Lüdtke's conceptualization of *Eigensinn* are usefully transferable to discussions of animal willfulness.

First, while *Eigensinn* may indeed be applicable to various kinds of social contexts, it is particularly well-gearred to illuminate the types of social relations that Lüdtke himself was interested in when developing the concept. *Eigensinn* emerged from Lüdtke's engagement with "domination as a social practice" and his attempts at making sense of the spectrum of everyday behaviors of historical actors living with(in) relations of domination.⁷³ Retaining this original focus on analyzing forms of behavior within structured arrangements of power avoids overstressing the concept, even as it simultaneously allows us to *extend* its reach into more-than-human social contexts in which some (human) beings organize and appropriate the capacities of (animal) others. Such a perspective does not require a flattening of different forms of subjectivity nor entail anthropomorphic projections of human agency (however delineated) but invites attention to the heterogeneous modalities through which living beings negotiate their terms of service from positions of subordinacy, and to the ways in which relations of domination are *co-produced* in and through these negotiations. Willfulness draws our attention to the practices of insistence observable in histories of everyday animal life under conditions of human control in which animals' desires and interests are impinged upon by regulatory forces and techniques put in place to contain and enlist them for anthropocentric purposes.

Second, Lüdtke's work on *Eigensinn* foregrounds "the nonverbal, body-related dimensions of behavior" based on an understanding of bodies "as sense organs that are both

⁷³ See Alf Lüdtke, "Einleitung: Herrschaft als soziale Praxis," in *Herrschaft als soziale Praxis: Historische und sozial-anthropologische Studien*, ed. Alf Lüdtke (Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1991); Alf Lüdtke and Alexandra Oeser, "Eigensinn and Domination in Liberal and Illiberal Societies," *History and Theory* 65, no. 1 (2026): 32–57.

meaningful and meaning-investing apart from meaningful words and symbols.”⁷⁴ This does not mean that *Eigensinn* is a “nonlinguistic” phenomenon per se – Lüdtké discusses inappropriate forms of address, ripostes, jokes, or asides that verbally undercut the hierarchical relations between workers and their superiors – but it underlines the importance of embodied, sensory engagements with the world as the principal site of both heteronomous demand and willful forms of “doing otherwise.” Notably, one of Lüdtké’s principal historical sources, German Enlightenment philosopher Christian Garve’s observations on the comportment of “unrefined” peasants toward their social betters, is suffused with recalcitrant corporeality and an absence of speech. “Everyone will no doubt remember having seen such faces among peasant boys,” Garve remarked, “where one or both eyes peer out furtively from beneath half-closed lids, their mouth hanging open and twisted into a mocking, somewhat stupid grin, the head pressed against the chest or at least lowered toward the ground as if wishing to hide itself,” but who when addressed stood “motionless and dumb like a stick,” with muscles “stiff and immovable.”⁷⁵ In such cases, it was as if the peasant’s entire being was wrapped in a stiffness that encompassed both body and “soul,” making him “dumb to all ideas presented to him.”⁷⁶ It was “this willfulness in him” – the fact of an “inferior” not listening to their “superior,” when even “the greatest clarity of his ideas, and all the power of truth contained in them, is unable to have any effect” – that aroused resentment even in the most well-meaning

⁷⁴ Lindenberger, “Eigen-Sinn, Domination and No Resistance.”

⁷⁵ Christian Garve, *Ueber den Charakter der Bauern und ihr Verhältniß gegen die Gutsherrn und gegen die Regierung. Drey Vorlesungen in der Schlesischen Oekonomischen Gesellschaft* (Wilhelm Gottlieb Korn, 1786), 52, my translation. Lüdtké also noted the importance of “non-verbal, bodily contacts” (*Eigen-Sinn*, 125) in discussing another important source, Protestant pastor Paul Göhre, who in 1890 spent three months working in a Chemnitz factory to learn about the lives of working-class people.

⁷⁶ Garve, *Ueber den Charakter der Bauern*, 55.

people.⁷⁷ For all its ties to contemporary speculations about the hidden topography of the mind, willfulness ultimately zeroed in on the body as a site of contestation. This emphasis on corporeality makes the concept useful for animal history, where various forms of bodily comportment hold particular relevance as traces of animal agency.

Third, Lüdtke's relational conceptualization of *Eigensinn* tied willful practices to the forms of meaning-making through which such practices were recognized and categorized by other social actors, especially by "higher-ups" in a given power structure compelled to address or govern them in some way. What Ahmed calls the "willfulness archive" – the dispersed traces of how willful bodies were identified as such and marked for intervention or discipline – may thus tell us something not only about how animal "doings otherwise" invited particular attributions of willfulness (as historically situated interpretations of animal conduct) but also how such attributions in turn shaped how animals could find room to maneuver within the normative frameworks that rendered their behavior legible, thereby co-shaping the social orders of work, care, and control into which they were integrated, and the specific pockets of freedom in constraint available to them.

Animal History and the Willfulness Archive

This article began with Nehemias Tjernagel's anecdotal reminiscences of "brute willfulness" in the context of nineteenth-century U.S. westward expansion, and in closing I want to return to this context. This is partly a choice of convenience, reflecting a principal focus of my own research, but looking at U.S. expansion – and specifically overland travel – also offers what I think is a fairly distinct angle on animal willfulness. The language of willfulness is common in

⁷⁷ Garve, *Ueber den Charakter der Bauern*, 55. Willfulness remained oblivious to sense and reason, Garve speculated, because its true source lay "not in the soul, but in the condition of the bodily organs" (56).

a variety of historical sources that include commentary on unwanted animal behavior. But I want to suggest that many sources operate with a grammar of willfulness in the form of certain narrative structures and forms of evaluative language even in the absence of obvious signal terms (“obstinate,” “self-willed,” “stubborn,” and the like).

Reflecting their broader status in a society dependent on animal-powered mobility – a fact that did not fundamentally change with the introduction of steam transit during the “transportation revolution” – domesticates were a key presence in all stages and contexts of U.S. expansion, and perhaps nowhere more visibly so than on the overland trails.⁷⁸ During the mid-century heyday of mass emigration, this network of routes traveled by westbound emigrants, including major trails like the California and Oregon Trail, gave rise to a mobile and notably more-than-human society that stretched over large parts of the American West. Overland travel was a months-long endeavor defined by an exceptionally close relationship of human-animal interdependency. When travelers praised their “faithful” animal companions, who, in the words of British explorer Isabella Bird, “exercise their intelligence for your advantage, and do their work rather as friends than as machines,” they presumed an alignment between the animals’ interests and their own under a shared purpose that included the voluntary submission to human directives.⁷⁹ What Susan Nance, borrowing from Jonathan Safran Foer, has called the “myth of animal consent to their use in the settling of the [American] West” can itself be understood as a specific iteration of the more comprehensive myth that domesticated

⁷⁸ See John D. Unruh, *The Plains Across: The Overland Emigrants and the Trans-Mississippi West, 1840-60* (University of Illinois Press, 1979); Diana L. Ahmad, *Success Depends on the Animals: Emigrants, Livestock, and Wild Animals on the Overland Trails, 1840-1869* (University of Nevada Press, 2016). On the transportation revolution, see George Rogers Taylor, *The Transportation Revolution, 1815-1860* (Rinehart, 1951).

⁷⁹ Isabella L. Bird, *A Lady's Life in the Rocky Mountains* (G. P. Putnam's Sons, 1879), 87.

animals had willingly bound themselves to humans by entering a tacit “contract,” trading sustenance and protection for labor and autonomy.⁸⁰

Yet as many travelers would come to realize, the fact that their animals were not “machines” did not mean that they were “friends” either, much less unconditional ones. Overland diaries and other texts on western travel demonstrate repeatedly that on western trails a firm control over one’s animal co-travelers was both imperative and difficult to achieve, as unwanted animal behaviors repeatedly forced travelers to confront the tenuous nature of human sovereignty when bereft of the structural and institutional supports employed to ensure compliance. Departing from St. Louis, Independence, or other jumping-off points along the Missouri River, travelers soon entered a fenceless ocean of grass, a prairie world of wide-open spaces – a “field of invitations” for animal reclamations of bodily and spatial autonomy.⁸¹ In such a context, human manipulations of animal bodies tended to be preventive rather than instructional or disciplinary in nature, aimed at suppressing possible manifestations of willfulness rather than attempting to exorcise willful tendencies through elaborate regimes of “education.”

If, according to Steward, the “power of self-movement defines the class of willed entities,” it was the power of asserting or withholding such self-movement that defined the sizable class of willful entities populating accounts of nineteenth-century overland travel.⁸² Picketing (tethering by a rope to a peg or stake) and hobbling (tying together the forelegs) were the best options to retain control over mules, oxen, or horses while also granting the animals the limited freedom of movement required for grazing. Such measures were reliable enough, until they weren’t. Stakes were pulled out of soft ground, knots slipped, ropes broke or were

⁸⁰ Susan Nance, *Rodeo: An Animal History* (University of Oklahoma Press, 2020), 9.

⁸¹ Rob Withagen, “The Field of Invitations,” *Ecological Psychology* 35, no. 3 (2023): 102–15.

⁸² Steward, *Metaphysics for Freedom*, 17.

chewed through. Some animals mastered the technique of the “hobble-walk,” covering surprising distances at surprising speeds with their legs tied together. Among the various animal troubles documented in Francis Parkman’s narrative of western travel in the 1840s was the “long and anxious search” for a band of escaped animals, who – led by an “incorrigible” horse aptly named after rebellious Ottawa chief Pontiac – were found “jumping along with hobbled feet, at a gait much more rapid than graceful.”⁸³ A similar “untoward incident” involved a group of animals who, in Parkman’s estimation, “had all set off for Fort Laramie, following the guidance of a mutinous old mule, and though many of them were hobbled, they had travelled three miles before they could be overtaken and driven back.”⁸⁴

The counterpart to such unwanted surplus of self-movement lay in its dogged refusal. While Parkman’s main culprit was another horse – Hendrick, “the very incarnation of perverse and brutish obstinacy”⁸⁵ – given that their reputation for willfulness was even acknowledged linguistically with a term of its own, it is not surprising that much of the particularly exasperated commentary was reserved for mules. Lansford Hastings, author of a widely read guidebook for overland emigrants, warned prospective travelers that if mules were generally known for their “extreme intractability” and “inflexible inertness,” the animals were likely to indulge in their mulishness “to a much greater extent than usual, upon this kind of expedition.”⁸⁶ George Kendall’s narrative of the ill-fated Texan Santa Fé Expedition of 1841,

⁸³ Francis Parkman, *The California and Oregon Trail: Being Sketches of Prairie and Rocky Mountain Life* (George P. Putnam, 1849), 55, 56.

⁸⁴ Parkman, *Oregon Trail*, 344, 345.

⁸⁵ Parkman, *Oregon Trail*, 111.

⁸⁶ Lansford W. Hastings, *The Emigrants’ Guide to Oregon and California* (George Conclin, 1845), 145. Defenders of the mule’s impugned character pointed to inadequate treatment or training as a cause of willfulness. As one agricultural advice book explained, “‘as obstinate as a mule’ has become a proverb, and like many other proverbs conveys only half a truth,” insisting that “[t]hese faults are all in training.” Charles

recounts the difficulties of English jurist Thomas Falconer – a “gentleman of high literary and scientific attainments” and “mild and agreeable manners” – with a “rickety, lame, self-willed” mule who insisted on following a “rigid system of economy . . . in the disbursement of her strength and speed,” perhaps offering an immediate role model to Falconer’s horse, whom Kendall describes as “self-willed as a pig” and “prone to have his own way, and take his own jog – preferring a walk or gentle trot to a canter.”⁸⁷ But it is Josiah Gregg’s image of the “athletic wagoner” straining nerve and muscle in the vain attempt to activate his “stubborn mule, while the brute as obstinately ‘sets back,’ determined not to ‘move a peg’ till his own good pleasure thinks it proper to do so,” that most readily captures the clash between human demands and animals’ insistence on corporeal self-direction in concrete physical struggles over the initiation or cessation, the speed, and the direction of movement.⁸⁸

While such intensely physical contests over bodily autonomy and heteronomy clearly resonate with an animals-as-resisters perspective, the language of willfulness was also employed in relation to forms of behavior that did not fit too well with the turning against of resistance but were more expressive of a distinct modality of turning elsewhere. Philip Leget Edwards, who traveled to Mexican California in 1837 as part of the Willamette Cattle Company

W. Dickerman and Charles L. Flint, *How to Make the Farm Pay: Or, The Farmer’s Book of Practical Information on Agriculture, Stock Raising, Fruit Culture, Special Crops, Domestic Economy & Family Medicine* (Zeigler, McCurdy, 1869), 338. “The mule has been called stubborn, willful and malicious,” noted another commentator, but such behaviors were the product of “savage, malicious and cruel treatment.” David Lyman, “Committee No. 26 – Jacks and Mules,” in *Transactions of the Connecticut State Agricultural Society, for the Year 1855* (Case, Tiffany, 1856), 77.

⁸⁷ George Wilkins Kendall, *Narrative of the Texan Santa Fé Expedition: Comprising a Description of a Tour through Texas, and across the Great Southwestern Prairies* (Harper and Brothers, 1844), 1:26, 42, 98.

⁸⁸ Josiah Gregg, *Commerce of the Prairies: Or, the Journal of a Santa Fé Trader* (H. G. Langley, 1844), 1:51.

(tasked with purchasing several hundred head of cattle for the settlers of Oregon's Willamette Valley), complained in his diary that the group's animals

were so obstinately lazy that every inch of ground we gained was contested. Hallooing, bawling, stones, clubs, and everything on which we could lay our hands, achieved every inch of our progress. They would turn off from the road, wander down the sides of the mountain, take refuge in the dense brush, stop to fight each other, and in short appeared willing to do anything but go quietly along the trail.⁸⁹

The language of willfulness here identifies a distinct space of agency, shaped by animals' insistence on pursuing their own interests and desires in dialogue with the opportunities for sensory and social diversion afforded by the trail environment. Edwards' characterization of the animals as "lazy" seems oddly inadequate to capture the variety of centrifugal activities they engage in, speaking to the tendency of human observers to fit such forms of animal waywardness or "anything but" activities into a familiar interpretative and evaluative framework of animal labor. Assessments like Edwards' thus both register animal subjectivity and construe a certain kind of animal subject based on a phenomenology of human sovereignty and its associated entitlements.

Jesse Quinn Thornton's account of his experiences as part of an Oregon- and California-bound wagon train includes a vignette involving two mischievous oxen, "Star and Golden, the two greatest rogues in my team," who had developed a habit of hampering the progress of the journey through a series of vanishing acts, which in this instance involved the disappearance into an undergrowth of "close and thick-leaved willows."

⁸⁹ Philip Leget Edwards, *California in 1837: Diary of Col. Philip L. Edwards, Containing an Account of a Trip to the Pacific Coast* (A. J. Johnston, 1890), 33.

They would be seen feeding until near the time for “catching up,” when suddenly they would be missing – in fact, they would be nowhere. . . . I have hunted for these oxen through every part of a thicket, as I believed; and would be about to give them over, as having been driven away by the Indians, when I would suddenly see them, not, perhaps, above fifteen feet from me, standing perfectly still, and looking directly at me. And when they saw that they had actually been discovered, they would of their own accord march out, with the most perfect alacrity and good-nature, and by their looks and actions, would plainly enough say, “Good-morning, good-morning. Oh, I am so glad to see you. You do not suspect us of hiding here?” Being thus fairly caught in their tricks, these rogues would go directly to the *kraal* [corral], and wait patiently for me to yoke them.⁹⁰

What Thornton refers to as the duo’s “favorite trick” points to a patterned repertoire of behavior that temporarily displaces their assigned work, rendered intelligible and evaluable through the moral idiom of “roguery.” Despite the humorous nature of the anecdote, Thornton’s repeated use of this term carries a more serious undertone. Originally used in the juridical context of English vagrancy laws, the term commonly referred to people accused of evading “honest” labor in favor of the “dishonest” life of wandering beggars (Thornton himself contrasts the bovine duo with the “honest and steady” behavior of their conspecific co-travelers).⁹¹ According to Jacques Derrida, unlike (for example) the German *Schurke*, the meaning of rogue as a term for “unprincipled outlaws” was eventually extended to “all nonhuman living beings”

⁹⁰ Jesse Quinn Thornton, *Oregon and California in 1848* (Harper and Brothers, 1849), 1:141. The duo’s “favorite trick” was not as idiosyncratic as we might infer from Thornton’s anecdote. As Howard Stansbury notes with regard to a mule who “must have hidden himself purposely in the thicket near the camp,” this was “a trick to which it is said some of these animals are addicted.” Howard Stansbury, *Exploration and Survey of the Valley of the Great Salt Lake of Utah* (Lippincott, Grambo, 1852), 245.

⁹¹ Thornton, *Oregon and California*, 1:141.

who exhibited “deviant or perverse” behavior.⁹² The common structural element which links Thornton’s bovine rogues to their human counterparts across the distances of space, time, and species is that their roguishness emerges in relation to a framework of accepted and acceptable behavior that includes as one of its defining features the policing of labor.

George Catlin’s narrative of his western travels in the 1830s – the basis of his ethnographic and artistic portraits of Plains Indians – demonstrates how domesticates’ who claimed space and time for themselves unsettled human imaginings of mutual service and obligation that operated with and from the assumption of willing animal subservience. Catlin’s account includes an episode detailing a 500-mile trip from Fort Gibson to St. Louis with his horse Charley, purchased from an Army officer stationed at the fort. According to Catlin, the two had acquired “a wonderful facility . . . of construing each other’s views and intentions” based on their “long and tried acquaintance,” a familiarity that approximated a “unity of *interest*.”⁹³ At sunset, Catlin usually halted by a stream, kindled a fire, made coffee, and fastened Charley to a picket that allowed him “to graze over a circle that he could inscribe at the end of his laso [*sic*].”⁹⁴ One evening, however, Charley managed to unpicket himself by slipping the rope over his head, enabling him to take “his supper at his pleasure, wherever he chose to prefer it.”⁹⁵ As night fell, Catlin tried to secure him, but Charley, “determined to enjoy

⁹² Jacques Derrida, *Rogues: Two Essays on Reason*, trans. Michael Naas and Pascale-Anne Brault (Stanford University Press, 2005), 93. While the first (1828) edition of Webster’s *American Dictionary* limits the term’s meaning to human beings, later dictionaries – including later editions of Webster’s – include entries for rogue elephants and horses.

⁹³ George Catlin, *Letters and Notes on the Manners, Customs, and Conditions of the North American Indians* (Wiley and Putnam, 1841), 2:89, original emphasis.

⁹⁴ Catlin, *Letters and Notes*, 2:90.

⁹⁵ Catlin, *Letters and Notes*, 2:90.

Fig. 3: Catlin and Charley on the prairie, observing a pack of wolves faintly visible on the horizon. George Catlin, *Letters and Notes on the Manners, Customs, and Conditions of the North American Indians*, vol. 2 (New York: Wiley and Putnam, 1841), plate 184.

a little freedom,” continually evaded him until dark.⁹⁶ Convinced he had lost his horse, Catlin went to sleep, only to awake in “a chill of horror” at the sight of what he took to be an Indian standing over him and about to relieve him of his scalp – before realizing it was Charley, who had returned “from feelings of pure affection, or from instinctive fear, or possibly, from a due share of both.”⁹⁷ The next morning, Catlin spotted his horse in the distance, “busily at work picking up his breakfast . . . along the bank of the creek,” but in spite of the “conclusive evidence” of the animal’s “attachment and dependence, which he had voluntarily given in the night,” Catlin soon found himself yet again engaged in “fruitless endeavours” to catch Charley,

⁹⁶ Catlin, *Letters and Notes*, 2:90.

⁹⁷ Catlin, *Letters and Notes*, 2:90.

who “continually tantalized me by turning around and around, and keeping out of my reach.”⁹⁸ It was only when Catlin packed up camp and pretended to leave without him that Charley, unwilling to be left behind, reversed course and followed, which “afforded us mutual relief from our awkward positions.”⁹⁹ Unnerved by this “alarming freak,” Catlin resolved to keep his horse under “strict authority” for the remainder of the journey “to avoid further tricks and experiments till we got to the land of cultivated fields and steady habits.”¹⁰⁰

In Roberto Marchesini’s words, Charley’s actions are those of a being who “creates situations” and “transforms the world into a field of opportunities” – who is “looking for something,” whether that something be that patch of prairie grass just beyond the range of the picket rope, freedom of movement as an end in itself, or something beyond the reach of such more intuitive interpretations.¹⁰¹ In their role as creators of unwanted situations, animals like Charley or the bovine duo of Star and Golden were able to carve out pockets of autonomy for themselves in a setting in which the actualization of human sovereignty was usually contingent upon a range of fairly rudimentary technologies of control. The preceding examples already indicate that the forms of insistence denoted by willfulness vary in form, intensity, and consequence. They can look like a rather effortless escape from the constraints of a picket rope or the recurring opportunity to frustrate human intentions by simply hiding from view. They can look like Tjernagel’s cow Salrei, a “truant among our cattle” known for regularly “inviting herself to choice grass-plots as far from home as possible.”¹⁰² They can look like bulls taking up “with strange herds for indefinite periods” or roaming the prairie “constantly spoiling for a

⁹⁸ Catlin, *Letters and Notes*, 2:90.

⁹⁹ Catlin, *Letters and Notes*, 2:91.

¹⁰⁰ Catlin, *Letters and Notes*, 2:90, 91.

¹⁰¹ Roberto Marchesini, “What Is Philosophical Ethology?,” *Humanimalia* 9, no. 1 (2017): 57.

¹⁰² Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 600.

fight with those of their kind.”¹⁰³ What underlies these different phenomena is that they mark “a space of expressive ownership,” one in which (even) animals living under conditions of human control insist, in whatever ways available to them, on being the owners of their own behavior.¹⁰⁴

Conclusion

Willfulness has accompanied resistance throughout historical regimes of human and animal governance. While some of its manifestations – including the proverbial “stubborn mule,” insistent on staying fixed in place despite human efforts to the contrary – approximate a logic of opposition, I have argued here that we should be careful not to conflate the two. Both resistance and willfulness name the hinge between subjective experience and the restrictive externalities that seek to shape or delimit it. But if resistance *confronts* these externalities – directly or indirectly, in ways that range from the dramatic to the barely noticeable – willfulness tends to course beneath or around them. As Lüdtkke explains, forms of willful insistence include a non-consent to “what is perceived as decisive or important in a given situation”: what actions are to be taken, in what sequence, at what pace, for what – and whose – purposes.¹⁰⁵

While I have suggested that willfulness might be most useful analytically when conceptualized not as an intrinsic quality but as an emergent phenomenon tied to relations of

¹⁰³ Tjernagel, “Pioneer Animal Lore,” 605, 603.

¹⁰⁴ Roberto Marchesini, *The Creative Animal: How Every Animal Builds Its Own Existence* (Springer, 2022), 123.

¹⁰⁵ “Eigen-Sinn und Alltagsgeschichte: Ein Gespräch von Kornelia Kończal mit Alf Lüdtkke und Thomas Lindenberger,” *Eigen-Sinn: Handlungsräume und Herrschaftspraxis*. Kollaborative Plattform zur Konzeption der Alltagsgeschichte im Anschluss an Alf Lüdtkke (1943-2019), October 12, 2021, <https://eigensinn.hypotheses.org/69>, my translation.

domination – including those of an “anthroparchal” nature¹⁰⁶ – I would argue that it is fundamentally anchored in the condition of animality, which is a condition of subjectivity, or what Marchesini calls an “interested condition” – having a point of view, affective investments, motivational desires, the capacity to initiate action based on perceptions and evaluations of the world.¹⁰⁷ Willful behavior, in other words, indexes the activities of beings guided by a keen yet elective openness to a world “strewn with opportunities and risks,” a world which they themselves change and shape through their own transformative inputs.¹⁰⁸ More precisely, it indexes such beings’ *insistence* on pursuing their own worldmaking practices within worlds that are quite distinctly *not* their own, configured according to parameters and priorities that do not or only partially and selectively address their interests.

From an animal historical perspective, willfulness can help us broaden our perspective on animals as history-making subjects. Just as Lüdtké’s *Eigensinn* opened up perspectives on a history of everyday life in which those relegated to the lower echelons of the social pecking order repeatedly insisted on distancing themselves from demands and impositions “from above,” or appropriated them for unintended purposes, animal willfulness directs us to histories of everyday animal life that were shaped by moments and patterns of agency through which animals appropriated the social and material orders that constrained them. The double aspect of, and constitutive tension between, willfulness as an evaluative human ascription and as a social phenomenon that tells us something about animals’ own ways of inhabiting such human-

¹⁰⁶ Sociologist Erika Cudworth defines as anthroparchal the “complex system of relationships in which the ‘environment’ (i.e. living entities which are both themselves systems, and embedded in eco-systems) is dominated through formations of social organization, which privilege the human.” Erika Cudworth, *Developing Ecofeminist Theory: The Complexity of Difference* (Palgrave Macmillan, 2005), 64.

¹⁰⁷ Marchesini, *Creative Animal*, 84.

¹⁰⁸ Marchesini, *Creative Animal*, 84.

imposed orders allows us to trace how animals' situated doings and human attempts to interpret, categorize, and manage them have continually reshaped one another.

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